
Unraveling the Fate of Microplastic Leachable Compounds: a Fast Screening using Ambient Pressure Ionization

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Abstract

The awareness among researchers towards the environmental impact of plastic, micro-, and nanoplastic pollution is rising, which is reflected by the growing number of publications studying their effects. However, the focus is mainly assigned on the particles, while the additives associated with plastics (e.g., plasticizers, etc.) are often overlooked. Such additives, essential for functionalizing plastics, can also pose hazardous effects towards biota and the environment. Therefore, advanced analytical methods are required to comprehend their impact. Although some studies are conducted, it is often hindered by time-consuming pretreatment steps (e.g., extractions) to discover the chemical content. To tackle laborious pretreatments, ambient pressure ionization techniques (e.g., Direct Analysis in Real-Time, DART) could provide promising solutions. These techniques can be coupled to mass spectrometry to rapidly and directly analyze liquid and solid samples at atmospheric pressure without any pretreatment. As a result, the appearance of additives in the plastic life cycle could be monitored facilitating circular economy, while elucidating the environmental impact.

Direct Analysis in Real-Time coupled to Mass Spectrometry (DART-MS) leads to direct ionization (predominantly (M+H)⁺ or (M-H)⁻ ions) of the volatilizable compounds in the sample. This results in complex mixed mass spectra that requires advanced approaches to identify the various compounds present. To enhance its use, the authors developed a workflow and database to quickly characterize various samples. By applying this workflow, sample preparation can be eliminated, enabling the swift detection of various chemicals in a single measurement. Consequently, it can support investigations of leachable compounds related to environmental plastic pollution, facilitating better understanding of their potential hazards. Acknowledgements – Financial support was obtained from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE innovation program, Upstream, under Grant Agreement No. 101112877.

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